

Synthesis and Characterisation of Divalent Metal Complexes of Diclofenac Sodium

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Diclofenac sodium(I), an effective and well-tolerated non-steroidal anti-inflammatory agent, is used in the treatment of rheumatoid arthritis and other inflammatory conditions¹. A variety of recent observations indicated that copper complexes when administered in conjunction with anti-inflammatory drugs exhibit synergistic activity². It has also been found that the Cu complexes of some antiarthritic drugs are themselves more active as anti-inflammatory agents than their parent compounds^{3,4}.

We therefore have undertaken the investigation of the interaction of Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} metal ions with diclofenac sodium. The study of the stereochemistries and chemical reactivity of the coordination compounds of the drug will help to determine the relationship between chemical structure and biological activity of the drug⁵.

Results and Discussion

Physical and analytical data of the complexes are listed in Table 1. The complexes are microcrystalline, high-spin, soluble in DMF and DMSO.

The Co^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes are of comparable thermal stability and the corresponding Ni^{II} complex is thermally less stable. Greater stability may be attributed to stabilisation by Jahn-Teller distortion for Co^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes as compared to the Ni^{II} complexes¹¹. The complexes have low conductance value in DMF at 10⁻³ M concentration (13.12, 10.66 and 9.84 $\Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$ respectively for the Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes) which indicates non-electrolytic nature of the complexes. The Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes exhibit magnetic moments values of 4.5, 3.7 and 1.7 B.M. respectively, indicating the presence of three, two and one unpaired electron, showing paramagnetic character.

Electronic spectra of the Co^{II} complex in DMF show bands at 18 416–18 691 and 31 055 cm^{-1} due to transition ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ and charge transfer respectively, suggesting an octahedral geometry⁶ around the metal ion. The Ni^{II} complex exhibits bands at 14 705–14 925 and shoulder at 25 641 cm^{-1} which may be assigned to the transitions ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F) \nu_2$ and ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P) \nu_3$ respectively, suggest-

TABLE 1 – ANALYTICAL DATA OF THE COMPLEXES

Compd./ (Colour)	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)				Dcomp Temp. °C
	M	C	H	N	
Co(C ₁₄ N ₁₀ Cl ₂ O ₂).2H ₂ O (Sand stone)	8.32 (8.59)	50.38 49.05	3.70 3.50	4.04 4.08)	245
Ni(C ₁₄ H ₁₀ NCl ₂ O ₂).2H ₂ O (Light green)	9.34 (8.57)	49.10 49.07	3.77 3.50	3.98 4.08)	115
Cu(C ₁₄ H ₁₀ NCl ₂ O ₂) ₂ .2H ₂ O (Cascade green)	9.28 (9.21)	47.56 48.72	3.48 3.09	4.06 3.73)	242

ing an octahedral geometry⁷ around Ni^{II}. The Cu^{II} complex shows one band at 13 812 cm⁻¹ due to transition ${}^2E_g \rightarrow {}^2T_{2g}$ suggesting a distorted octahedral geometry⁸ and a band at 35 587 cm⁻¹ is assigned to intra-ligand charge transfer transition.

In the ir spectra, the Co^{II} complex exhibits one double hump at 3 200–3 550 cm⁻¹ and the Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes exhibit broad bands at ~ 3 400 cm⁻¹ followed by sharp peaks at ~ 1 600, ~ 830 cm⁻¹, assignable to OH stretching, bending and rocking vibrations respectively, indicating the presence of coordinated water molecules in the complexes⁹. The ligand bands at 3 400 (NH) and 1 575 cm⁻¹ (C=O) shifted by ± 15 –20 cm⁻¹ in the complexes, indicating the coordination through these groups. In the far-ir region, the chelates show new band at 470–450 and 440–430 cm⁻¹ comparable with ν_{M-N} and ν_{M-O} respectively¹⁰.

Experimental

Metal chlorides (AnalaR) and diclofenac sodium (Lupin Laboratory, Aurangabad) were used.

The Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} diclofenac complexes were prepared according to the following procedure. To an hot aqueous solution of the metal salt, a solution of the ligand in the same solvent in 1 : 2 stoichiometric ratio were added. The solution was refluxed for 1 h on a water-bath. After a few minutes, the resulting precipitate was washed with hot distilled water and dried under reduced pressure at room temperature for 24 h. Molar conductance was determined using an Elico CM 82T instrument. Magnetic susceptibility was measured on Gouy's balance at room temperature using CuSO₄·5H₂O as calibrant: diamagnetic corrections were applied using Pascal's constant. Ir spectra were recorded

on a Shimadzu IR-470 spectrophotometer.

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